

BIOTRAILS

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Glossary of terms and abbreviations

Abbreviation / Term	Description
AR6	Sixth Assessment Report
BCS	Biodiversity, climate and society
C3S	Copernicus Climate Change Service
CC	Correlation Coefficient
CMIP6	Coupled Model Intercomparison Project Phase 6
CRA	Climate Risk Assessment
ERA5	ECMWF Reanalysis v5
GCM	Global Climate Model
GDP	Gross Domestic Product
IPCC	Intergovernmental Panel on Climate Change
RMSE	Root Mean Square Error
SSP	Shared Socioeconomic Pathway

ABSTRACT

This technical document presents the methodological framework developed under Deliverable 3.8 Climate Projections Report (B) of the BIOTRAILS project. The report details the refined approach for assessing climate risks in four selected value chains — cocoa produced in Peru, forest-based cultural products created by Indigenous communities in Brazil, fisheries and aquaculture products supplied by Greece, and gold mined in Ghana.

The methodology is grounded in the conceptual framework of the Intergovernmental Panel on Climate Change (IPCC AR6) and employs a composite-indicator approach integrating hazard, exposure, and vulnerability dimensions. It combines climate projections from CMIP6 models with geospatial, socio-economic, and sectoral datasets to evaluate how climatic changes may affect natural resources, production systems, and communities.

The framework provides a transparent, replicable, and flexible structure to quantify and map climate risks across diverse value chains. It aims to facilitate transformative adaptation by providing evidence-based insights that can inform decision-making at local, regional, and global levels.

1. INTRODUCTION

1.1 RATIONAL FOR CLIMATE RISK ASSESSMENT IN VALUE CHAINS

Climate change is intensifying pressures on ecosystems, livelihoods, and production systems that depend on natural resources. Global value chains, particularly those involving agriculture, aquaculture, forestry, and mining, are highly sensitive to changes in temperature, precipitation, and extreme weather events. The BIOTRAILS project seeks to integrate biodiversity, climate, and social dimensions (the BCS nexus) to understand how these interdependencies affect sustainability and resilience.

The four BIOTRAILS value chains represent different ecological and socio-economic contexts: cocoa cultivation in Peru, Indigenous handicrafts in the Brazilian Amazon, fisheries and aquaculture in Greece, and artisanal gold mining in Ghana. Each value chain is directly linked to biodiversity and local livelihoods, making them ideal systems to test and refine a harmonised climate risk assessment (CRA) methodology.

The full version of the deliverable can be accessed through this link: https://biotrailsproject.eu/wp-content/uploads/2025/03/BIOTRAILS_D3.8_Climate-Projections-Report-B.pdf

1.2 OBJECTIVES AND SCOPE OF THE METHODOLOGICAL FRAMEWORK

The primary objective of this methodological framework is to develop a coherent, scientifically robust, and operational approach for assessing climate risks to the BIOTRAILS value chains. Specifically, it aims to quantify climate-related hazards using advanced projections (CMIP6), assess the exposure of economic and ecological assets to those hazards, evaluate the vulnerability

of socio-economic systems and communities, and integrate these three components into a composite climate risk index. The methodology has been designed for scalability, enabling replication across other regions and value chains within or beyond the BIOTRAILS framework.

1.3 CONCEPTUAL FRAMEWORK

The BIOTRAILS climate risk assessment (CRA) follows the conceptual framework of the Intergovernmental Panel on Climate Change (IPCC). In the Sixth Assessment Report (AR6), risk is defined as the potential for adverse consequences for human or ecological systems, resulting from the dynamic interaction between climate-related hazards and the exposure and vulnerability of the affected systems [1].

A climate-related **hazard** refers to the potential occurrence of a natural or human-induced physical event or trend that may cause injury, loss of life, or damage to property, infrastructure, livelihoods, ecosystems, and environmental resources, including floods, droughts, heatwaves, and other extreme weather events. Hazards may manifest suddenly, as in heatwaves or heavy rainfall, or gradually, as in land degradation or erosion compounded by multiple climate stresses [2]. **Exposure** represents the presence of people, ecosystems, infrastructure, or economic, social, and cultural assets in areas potentially affected by hazards [3]. Consequently, the greater the presence of a system in a given area, the higher the exposure. The greater the presence of a system in a given area, the higher its exposure, whereas areas with no exposure face no associated climate risk. **Vulnerability** is the propensity of a system to be adversely affected, encompassing sensitivity, susceptibility to harm, and limited capacity to cope or adapt [2], [4]. **Sensitivity** measures the degree to which a system is affected by climate variability or change, either directly (e.g., reduced crop yields) or indirectly (e.g., increased coastal flooding) [2]. **Adaptive capacity** represents the ability of systems, institutions, humans, and other organisms to adjust to potential damage, exploit opportunities, or respond to consequences [2].

A qualitative formula illustrates the relationship among risk, hazard, exposure, and vulnerability when evaluating climate risk.

$$\text{Risk} = \text{Hazard} \times \text{Exposure} \times \text{Vulnerability}$$

Figure 1: The conceptual framework of Climate Risk Assessment in the BIOTRAILS project adapted from the IPCC [5].

1.3.1 Methodological Framework

Each risk component is quantified through composite indicators derived from sub-indicators specific to each value chain. Hazard indicators capture climate-related threats using projected climate variables, exposure indicators quantify the spatial presence of relevant systems, and

vulnerability indicators assess socio-economic and environmental susceptibility, including sensitivity and adaptive capacity. Indicators are processed in three stages: normalisation, weighting, and aggregation.

In the normalisation stage, the values of the indicators, which may be expressed in different measurement units, are standardised to a common scale to ensure comparability. The normalisation scale is defined within a numerical range of 0 to 5, with each value corresponding to one of five distinct risk levels, from low to high, as illustrated in Table 1.

Table 1: Qualitative and numerical scale of risk indicators.

Qualitative scale	Numerical scale
Low	$0 < \text{Risk} \leq 1$
Low to Medium	$1 < \text{Risk} \leq 2$
Medium	$2 < \text{Risk} \leq 3$
Medium to High	$3 < \text{Risk} \leq 4$
High	$4 < \text{Risk} \leq 5$

1.3.2 Model validation and ensemble

Climate model outputs often differ from observational or reanalysis data, a discrepancy known as bias. These biases vary across geographical regions, meaning that model performance differs spatially. To detect such biases and identify the models that perform best in each case study area, regional-specific model validation is required. This process involves comparing model hindcasts for the historical period with observational or reanalysis datasets for each parameter and pilot region [9].

For this study, the fifth generation atmospheric reanalysis dataset (ERA5) by the European Centre for Medium – Range Weather Forecasts (ECMWF) was used [10]. ERA5 provides hourly data on atmospheric, land-surface, and sea-state parameters at $0.25^\circ \times 0.25^\circ$ resolution, covering the period from 1940 to the present, with daily updates available five days behind real time.

Model validation was based on statistical metrics such as the Root Mean Square Error (RMSE) and the Correlation Coefficient (CC). RMSE and CC were calculated for all models against ERA5 data, and models performing above a predefined threshold were selected for further analysis.

The best-performing models for each region were combined into a model ensemble. Ensemble outputs capitalize on the strengths of multiple models, reducing biases and uncertainties inherent in individual models and improving the reliability of projections. Average conditions were then calculated for the mid-term (2041–2060) and long-term (2015–2100) periods, allowing comparison with the reference period (1995–2014).

2. DEVELOPMENT OF RISK INDICATORS

2.1 HAZARD

Within the BIOTRAILS project, potential hazards are assessed using a set of climate indicators capturing both slow-onset changes (e.g., gradual temperature increases, reduced precipitation)

and extreme events (e.g., heatwaves, floods, droughts). Indicator selection followed a comprehensive literature review and consultation with case study leaders. For cocoa production in Peru, hazards include changes in mean and extreme temperature, precipitation, and evapotranspiration, affecting crop yields, suitable cultivation areas, and soil microbiology [11], [12], [13], [14], [15], [16]. For indigenous handicrafts in Brazil, climate change threatens the availability of plant-based raw materials, including fibers, seeds, and dyes, through altered precipitation and temperature patterns [17]. Indigenous communities also provide critical ecosystem stewardship, contributing to climate mitigation and adaptation [18],[19]. In Mediterranean fisheries and aquaculture, hazards include rising sea surface temperatures and salinity fluctuations, affecting species composition, reproduction, metabolism, migration, disease incidence, and aquaculture productivity [7], [20], [21], [22], [23], [24], [25], [26], [27], [28]. For gold mining in Ghana, climate hazards comprise changes in temperature, precipitation, and humidity, impacting worker safety, energy demands, slope stability, water availability, and operational costs, with additional implications for local communities [29], [30], [31], [32].

The selected hazard indicators for each case study are presented in Table and further analysed afterwards.

Table 2: Climatic hazard indicators examined for the BIOTRAILS case studies

Variable	Peru	Brazil	Greece	Ghana
Near-surface air temperature	X	X		X
Daily maximum near-surface air temperature	X			X
Daily minimum near-surface air temperature	X			
Heat Stress Days	X	X		X
Evaporation including sublimation and transpiration	X			
Relative humidity				X
Precipitation	X	X		
Heavy precipitation	X	X		X
Consecutive dry days	X	X		X
Sea-surface temperature			X	
Sea-surface salinity			X	

These indicators include both basic variables (e.g., near-surface temperature, precipitation) and derived indices (e.g., heavy precipitation, consecutive dry days, heat stress days), which provide insights into the changing frequency and intensity of climatic extremes.

The temporal evolution of the selected hazards is assessed through climate model projections. General Circulation Models (GCMs) are used to simulate the interactions among Earth's climate components and project global climate dynamics. Three Shared Socioeconomic Pathways (SSP1-2.6, SSP2-4.5, and SSP3-7.0) were selected to capture a range of possible future conditions, from low-emission to high-emission trajectories.

Comparisons were made between future (2015–2100) and reference (1995–2014) periods, focusing on two future horizons: 2041–2060 and 2081–2100. Mean differences between scenarios and the reference period were summarized in tables, while spatial distributions for 2041–2060 were visualized through maps. This mid-century period was prioritized as it provides actionable insights for the timely design and implementation of adaptation policies.

2.2 EXPOSURE

In Peru, exposure for cocoa production is measured as the percentage of land under cocoa cultivation, representing the share of cocoa-planted area relative to the total harvested area in the region.

Table 3: Assessment of exposure by province in Ucayali, Peru.

Province	Area inhabited by indigenous (%)	Harvested area (%)	Exposure
Padre Abad	20,894	70	High
Coronel Portillo	5,102	17	Medium
Atalaya	3,667	12	Medium
Purús	36	0.1	Low

In Rondônia, Brazil, exposure for sustainable forest-based handicrafts combines the spatial distribution of indigenous populations with the extent of forested areas that supply raw materials.

Table 4: Assessment of exposure in Rondônia, Brazil.

Immediate region	Area inhabited by indigenous (%)	Exposure
Porto Velho	37.2	High
Ariquemes	5.2	Low to Medium
Jaru	0.1	Low
Ji-Paraná	19.9	Medium
Cacoal	29.4	Medium to High
Vilhena	8.2	Low to Medium

For Greece, fisheries exposure is based on the quantity of fish catches, expressed as the proportion of catches in each fishing zone relative to the national total.

Table 5: Spatial distribution of catches (%) per fishing area and fishing zone.

Fishing zone	Exposure	Fishing	Exposure
	Quantity of catches (%)		Quantity of catches (%)
Crete (1)	Low (2)	Pagasetikos (9)	Low (0.1)
Dodecanese (2)	Low to Medium (4.4)	Kyparissia (10)	Low (0.4)
Strymonikos (3)	High (23.3)	Lamia Gulf (11)	Medium to High (11.6)
Thermaikos (4)	High (23)	Evia and Sporades (12)	Low to Medium (2.9)
Argolida and Saronikos Gulf (5)	Medium (9.3)	Cyclades (13)	Low to Medium (3.9)
Laconian Gulf (6)	Low (0.4)	Amvrakikos (14)	Low (0.8)
Epirus and Corfu (7)	Low (1.6)	Lesvos, Chios, Samos, Ikaria (15)	Low to Medium (3.3)
Kefalonia, Zakynthos (8)	Medium (7.9)	Korinthia (16)	Low (2.1)

Aquaculture exposure is measured as the share of approved aquaculture production tonnage in each region relative to the national total.

Table 6: Number of aquaculture units and approved tonnage per administrative region

Administrative region	Approved tonnage (%)	Exposure
Eastern Macedonia and Thrace	0	No
Central Macedonia	2.8	Low to Medium
Western Macedonia	0	No
Epirus	8.4	Medium
Thessaly	0.7	Low
Central Greece	31.5	High
Ionian Islands	7.7	Medium
Western Greece	9.1	Medium
Peloponnese	15.3	Medium to High
Attica	7.6	Medium
North Aegean	5.6	Medium
South Aegean	11.3	Medium to High
Crete	0	No

In Ghana, exposure for gold mining is defined as the proportion of the pilot region occupied by mining sites.

Table 7: Assessment of exposure per administrative region in Ghana.

Administrative region	Exposure Share of area occupied by mining sites(%)	Administrative region	Exposure Share of area occupied by mining sites(%)
Ahafo	High (21.7)	Northern East	Low (0.2)
Ashanti	Medium to High (11.2)	Oti	Low to Medium (2.7)
Bono	Medium (6.4)	Savannah	Low (0.3)
Bono East	No (0)	Upper East	Medium to High (17.1)
Central	Medium (9.4)	Upper West	Medium to High (12.2)
Eastern	Medium (9.7)	Volta	No (0)
Greater Accra	Medium (8.4)	Western	High (22.4)
Northern	No (0)	Western North	Medium to High (14)

2.3 VULNERABILITY

For cocoa production in Peru, sensitivity reflects local dependence on cocoa for employment and GDP, while adaptive capacity considers socioeconomic factors such as income, poverty, education, and population age. Higher sensitivity or lower adaptive capacity increases vulnerability.

Table 8: Vulnerability assessment, Ucayali region in Peru.

Vulnerability indicator	Facts	Score
Contribution to global cocoa production	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Peru is the 8th-largest global producer (2.9% of global production). 2nd-leading producer of organic cocoa. 	Medium to High
Importance for the national economy	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Cocoa is the 3rd most exported product in Ucayali Cocoa contributes 0.6% to the national GDP. 	Low to Medium
Dependency of the local population	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Cocoa producers make up 4% of all agricultural producers in Peru. 	Low

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> In Ucayali, cocoa workers account for about 1.7% of the workforce. 	
Share of smallholder farmers	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> 91% of cocoa producers manage <3 ha. 	High
Age, gender and education level	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Average farmer age is 50 years. Primary education in majority. Women make up 41% of producers. 	High
Economic capacity of the local population	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Per capita GDP is 56% of the world average and 69% of the South America average. 28% of the population lives in poverty. 	Medium to High

In Rondônia, Brazil, vulnerability for indigenous handicraft communities considers dependence on forest resources as sensitivity, and community infrastructure, education access, and alternative incomes as adaptive capacity. This identifies communities most susceptible to climate impacts on raw materials and ecosystem services.

Table 9: Vulnerability assessment, Rondônia, Brazil.

Vulnerability Indicator	Facts	Score
Importance for the local population	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> The artisan sector represents the 2nd largest employer Important cultural and economic activity 	Medium to High
Dependency on natural resources	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Handicraft production depends heavily on forest resources like plant fibers, seeds, and natural dyes. 	High
Land use change and deforestation	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Rondônia is the most deforested state in Brazil 76% tree cover loss in Porto Velho. 	Medium to High
Age, gender and education level	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Sector dominated by women with low educational attainment Structural inequalities. 	High
Economic capacity of the local population	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> GDP per capita is 89% below South America's average and 72% below global average. 27.4% live in poverty. 	Medium to High

For fisheries and aquaculture in Greece, sensitivity is based on reliance on fishing and aquaculture for income, employment, and food security, amplified by changes in species distribution and disease prevalence. Adaptive capacity includes technological support, institutional frameworks, and financial resources. High sensitivity and low adaptive capacity under changing sea conditions increase vulnerability.

Table 10: Vulnerability assessment of aquaculture, Greece.

Vulnerability indicator	Facts	Vulnerability
Contribution at Mediterranean level	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Greece operates the second-largest fleet 8.5% of the Mediterranean's total gross tonnage. 	Medium to High
Importance for the national economy	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> The fisheries sector accounts for only 0.3% of Greece's GDP. 	Low
Dependency of the local population	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Fisheries employ 0.4% of the workforce Important for the cultural identity of rural coastal communities. 	Medium
Share of small-scale fisheries	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> 94% of vessels, 52% of landings and 81% of employment 	High
Thermal tolerance of fish	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Key species are moderately vulnerable to warming seas. 	Medium

Economic capacity of the local population	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Greece's GDP per capita is 65% of the European average. 19% of population lives in poverty. 	Medium
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For gold mining in Ghana, vulnerability considers economic and social dependence on mining and operational sensitivity to hazards such as flooding, heat stress, and water scarcity. Adaptive capacity is reflected by institutional preparedness, safety protocols, and infrastructure. Areas with low adaptive capacity and high sensitivity are most vulnerable.

Table 11: Vulnerability assessment of aquaculture, Greece.

Vulnerability indicator	Facts	Vulnerability
Contribution of national gold production at global level	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> 6% of global production. 12% of Africa's output. Production exceeds the average gold-producing countries (3%) 	Medium
Importance of gold for the national economy	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Gold contributes 7.2% to the national GDP. Gold accounts for 56% of the total mining output, within the mining sector. 	Medium
Dependency of the local population on gold mining	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> 8.8% of Ghana's workforce depends on gold mining for their livelihoods. 	Medium to High
Share of small-scale gold mining	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ASM contributes 36% of Ghana's annual gold production. 	Medium to High
Age, gender and education level of miners	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Average farmer age is 20–39 years. Majority have low education level. Women make up 9.8% of total miners, 22% of legal ESM miners and 50% of the galamsey population. 	High
Economic capacity of the local population	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Peru's GDP per capita is 56% of the world average and 69% of the South American average. 27.5% of the population lives in poverty. 	High

2.4 OVERALL RISK

In this section, the results of the comprehensive climate risk assessment for the BIOTRAILS value chains are presented, under SSP1–2.6, SSP2–4.5, and SSP3–7.0 and for the periods 2041–2060 and 2081–2100.

For cocoa production in Ucayali, Peru, the results indicate that most provinces are projected to experience a Medium risk level under all scenarios, with Padre Abad showing the largest increase. Under SSP3–7.0, its risk rises from Medium to High by 2041–2060 and remains High by 2081–2100. Coronel Portillo reaches Medium–High under SSP2–4.5 (2081–2100) and SSP3–7.0. Atalaya remains Medium risk in most scenarios, reaching Medium–High under SSP3–7.0 (2081–2100). Purús remains Low–Medium throughout. Differences in risk mainly reflect the spatial distribution of cocoa cultivation. Adaptation should focus on Padre Abad, Coronel Portillo, and Atalaya.

The climate risk assessment for sustainable forest-based cultural products in Rondônia shows that most regions face a Medium risk level, with increasing risks under higher emissions scenarios. Porto Velho, Ariquemes, Ji-Paraná, and Cacoal reach High risk by 2081–2100 under SSP3–7.0. Porto Velho and Ji-Paraná increase steadily, reaching Medium–High under SSP2–4.5 (2041–2100) and SSP3–7.0 (2041–2060) before escalating to High. Ariquemes follows a similar trajectory, while Cacoal stabilizes at Medium–High. Jaru remains Low–Medium, and Vilhena Medium due to lower hazard. Risk differences largely reflect the area populated by Indigenous people. Adaptation should prioritize Porto Velho, Ariquemes, Ji-Paraná, and Cacoal.

The climate risk assessment for fisheries in Greece indicates an overall increasing trend in risk levels, particularly under SSP3-7.0. Strymonikos, Thermaikos, Lamia Gulf, Argolida, and Saronikos reach High risk by 2081–2100. Crete, Dodecanese, Kefalonia–Zakynthos, Cyclades, Evia–Sporades, and Lesvos–Chios–Samos–Ikaria rise from Medium mid-century to Medium–High late century. Epirus, Corfu, and Korinthia follow a similar trend. Pagasitikos remains Low–Medium, while Laconian Gulf, Kyparissia, and Amvrakikos reach at most Medium. Adaptation should focus on high-risk northern and central zones.

The results for Greece’s aquaculture sector reveal increasing risks across most administrative regions, particularly under higher-emission scenarios. Central Greece, the Peloponnese, Attica, the North and South Aegean regions show a notable risk increase, transitioning from Low to Medium in 2041–2060 under SSP1-2.6 to Medium to High by 2081–2100 under SSP3-7.0. Other regions, such as Epirus, Thessaly, the Ionian Islands, and Western Greece, exhibit a gradual increase in risk, reaching Medium levels by the late century under SSP3-7.0. Macedonia, Thrace, Western Macedonia and Crete remain unaffected due to a lack of exposure.

The climate risk assessment for gold mining in Ghana's administrative regions vary under different SSP scenarios and time periods. Ahafo, Ashanti, Central, and Eastern regions show Medium–High risk, reaching High under SSP3-7.0 by 2081–2100. Bono East, Northern, and Volta face no risk due to lack of exposure. Differences mainly reflect the location of gold mining sites, with central and southern regions most affected.

Detailed tables of the overall risk per scenario and time period are provided in the Annex for all value chains.

3. DISCUSSION AND CONCLUSIONS

The BIOTRAILS climate risk assessment methodology provides a clear and practical framework for combining climate, environmental, and socio-economic data in a single analysis. It builds on earlier approaches by using multi-model CMIP6 projections to quantify hazards, applying transparent methods for scaling and weighting indicators, and integrating both socio-economic and ecological vulnerability. The framework also allows for adaptation measures tailored to specific sectors while maintaining a consistent overall structure.

Overall, this approach supports the creation of evidence-based adaptation strategies, helping decision-makers identify the most effective actions to strengthen resilience across biodiversity-dependent value chains.

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